

Photoinduced Catalytic Reactions of Organic Compounds on Zinc Oxide and Tungsten Trioxide Powders and Electrodes

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Different electrode preparations with polycrystalline zinc oxide and tungsten trioxide have been attempted and their performance studied. Even though both the oxides are n-type semiconductors, their behaviour towards dissolved species in the electrolyte is different. The pretreatment of the material and the mode of preparation of the electrodes influence the performance of the catalyst. Photoinduced catalytic reactions of organic compounds like alcohols, amines, amides, etc. on these semiconducting oxide powders in suspension are compared with similar photoelectrocatalytic reactions.

THERE are several possible photoinduced reactions that can, in principle, be carried out at semiconductor surfaces. The photodecomposition of water into hydrogen and oxygen over semiconductors is one of the very vigorously pursued areas of research in recent times¹⁻³. Other than the photolysis of water ($\Delta G > 0$), liquid junction solar cells with one electron redox couples in solution ($\Delta G = 0$) and photosynthetic cells ($\Delta G > 0$), there are systems which are solely photocatalytic in which $\Delta G < 0$. In the last case the semiconductor accelerates the reaction. In practice these photocatalytic systems in which semiconductor particles are suspended in a liquid medium are a large collection of microphotoelectrocatalytic cells⁴. These systems are mainly employed for synthesis of energy rich materials from cheap starting materials, waste substances, biomass, etc., at the cost of light energy^{5,6}. The final products include H_2 , H_2O_2 , hydrocarbons, amino acids, halogens, carbonyl compounds, etc. The mechanism of reactions in photocatalytic systems and photoelectrocatalytic cells have so much in common that understanding one helps in designing the other for useful purposes.

Photosynthesis of H_2O_2 has been studied on various semiconductor powders such as TiO_2 ^{7,8}, ZnO ^{9,10}, CdS ^{10,11}, etc. Morrison and Freund investigated photocatalytic reactions of aqueous HCOOH on ZnO employing electrochemical measurements¹². Addition of HCOOH caused a current doubling effect and the HCOOH was converted to CO_2 and H_2O_2 . Harbour and Hair¹³ and subsequently Fujishima *et al*¹⁴ studied these reactions extensively. Recently Rao *et al*⁷ reported the production of H_2O_2 as well as H_2 on irradiating ZnO grains in water. Light induced catalytic reactions of organic substances on oxide semiconductors have been reported by several authors¹⁵⁻²². A free radical mechanism was identified in photocatalytic systems whereas an ionic electron transfer followed by a free radical mechanism has been suggested for

the same systems in the photoelectrocatalytic mode²³.

In this paper we report some of our findings on the photoinduced catalytic reactions of organic substances in aqueous medium on ZnO and WO_3 powders as well as polycrystalline electrodes prepared from them. ZnO and WO_3 are semiconductor oxides with band gaps of 3.2 eV (absorption max at 365 nm) and 2.7 eV (absorption max at 420 nm), respectively. Both oxides are n-type semiconductors, but with notable differences in their behaviour towards reactions of organic compounds. Further, WO_3 is photochromic, can exist in several non-stoichiometric forms and exhibits a very low photodissociation in aqueous media.

Experimental

The experimental set up used for photocatalytic studies of the semiconductor powder suspensions is the same as described elsewhere¹⁵⁻¹⁸. The cell used for the photoelectrochemical studies is given below :

Pt, semiconductor oxide/0.1M KCl, aq. org.
substrate 0.1M KCl/Pt

The cell consists of a two compartment pyrex vessel with a KCl saturated agar bridge and provision for bubbling the required gases through the electrolyte. The ultra violet light source is a 200 watt Spindler-Hoyer high pressure mercury arc lamp and the visible light source is a 1000 watt Philips halogen lamp. For potentiostatic studies, a Wenking potentiostat (model 70HP10) and for voltage and current measurements, a Keithley 610B electrometer have been used. In the three electrode system SCE is used as the reference electrode.

All the organic chemicals used (B.D.H., S.M. or E.M.) are purified by standard methods. ZnO (M & B) and WO_3 (Koch-Light) powders are used as received.

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Electrode preparation :

Different simple electrode preparations with polycrystalline oxide material have been attempted since the PEC reaction mechanism of single crystals and polycrystalline materials are usually identical. The standardization of these methods helps in preparing inexpensive stable electrodes for easy and quick qualitative or mechanistic studies of different electrode materials and electrolyte combinations.

Slurry electrode and oxide deposited from a colloidal solution : An oxide paste prepared by moistening ZnO or WO₃ with 0.1 M KCl is painted over a clean Pt foil and is partially dried. Alternately a suspension of the oxide (0.5 g) in water (2-3 ml) is subjected to ultrasonic vibrations to obtain a colloidal solution and applied over a Pt foil which is subsequently dried at 110°. These electrodes give reproducible results but the current produced is low.

Semiconductor-liquid crystal electrodes : Two liquid crystals, namely, cholesteryl oleate and *p*-(*n*-butoxy)benzoic acid are used as binders. The method of preparing these electrodes has been reported earlier²⁴.

Electrodes prepared with added flux material : Electrodes are prepared by painting a uniform paste of ZnO together with 3% weight of CdCl₂ moistened with 5% aqueous solution of a non-ionic detergent (Triton-X) on a Pt foil and heating it at 480° for 2 hr in N₂ atmosphere. This method is similar to the method employed by Hodes *et al*²⁵ for preparing chalcogenide electrodes. Addition of flux materials altered the properties of WO₃ and so this is not a good method for preparing WO₃ electrodes. Alternately, WO₃ electrodes have been prepared by painting an aqueous paste of WO₃ over a Pt foil and heating at 400° for 1 hr. WO₃ particles adhere to the metal surface very well and the electrodes are very active.

Pellet electrodes : ZnO pellets (1 cm diam ; 0.2 cm thick ; 0.5 t/cm² pressure) are made and heated to 1100° for 3 hr. They are polished with emery paper and etched in conc. HNO₃ for 15 sec. The WO₃ pellets are heated at 700° in air for 20 hr. Electrode contacts are made through a copper wire using In-Ga alloy. Except the side to be illuminated, all the other surfaces of the pellet are covered with epoxy resin and used as the electrode.

Thermal oxidation of tungsten : Tungsten foil (0.5 cm²) is cleaned thoroughly and heated in air at 800° for 30 min. One side of the foil is then polished with emery paper to get a clean metal surface and electrode contacts are made with copper wire and In-Ga alloy.

WO₃ films produced by spray pyrolysis : A 20% ammonium tungstate solution is sprayed over a hot Pt foil (400°) and the resulting thin film used as an electrode.

Preparation of lithium and aluminium doped ZnO samples : The method of doping^{17,26} consists of wetting the dry powdered ZnO with approximately the same weight of an aqueous solution containing the required amount of doping salt [Al(NO₃)₃ or

LiNO₃]. After drying at 110°, the sample is heated at 450° for 10 hr. Heating the samples at higher temperature causes sintering of ZnO which reduces the catalytic activity. The doped samples are analysed for the actual concentration of the dopants.

Results and Discussion**1. Photoinduced reactions in particulate systems : ZnO :**

Several photoinduced catalytic reactions have been studied and reported^{6,15-18,28}. In this section we summarise the important findings of these studies. The reactions studied include the oxidation of benzyl alcohol, benzhydrol, aliphatic alcohols, amides, aromatic amines, etc. in aqueous and non-aqueous media. All these reactions take place through free radical mechanisms. Radicals form from a charge transfer complex or exciplex involving the excited ZnO. Light and oxygen are found to be essential for the reactions. Formation of superoxide anion, O₂⁻, is proposed in all these reaction schemes. On absorption of light of proper energy an electron of ZnO is excited from the valence band to the conduction band. This electron is subsequently captured by the adsorbed O₂ to form O₂⁻. In heterogeneously photocatalysed reactions of alcohols, amides or amines on ZnO, the effect of light is to reduce an adsorbed oxygen molecule which subsequently reacts to form H₂O₂ which is one of the major products. Primary alcohols gave the corresponding aldehydes while secondary alcohols produced ketones. Yesodharan *et al*²⁷ reported C₆H₅CH₂ as one of the products from benzyl alcohol showing a disproportionation in addition to the formation of C₆H₅CHO and H₂O₂. The products and the rates depend on the solvent ; the more polar the medium, the higher the rate of reaction. Hence, polar intermediates with O₂⁻ as the active entity are suggested.

In cyclohexane medium the concentration of H₂O₂ showed an oscillation with time of irradiation^{17,28}. The critical concentrations at which the oscillation starts and stops depend on the substrates and other specie present in the system. Amides, amines and hydrocarbons like naphthalene inhibit the reaction.

On the other hand, reactions of benzhydrol were found to be autocatalytic due to the product, benzophenone²⁸. Amides are found to form surface complexes through the carbonyl oxygen thereby inhibiting other photoinduced catalytic reactions. Benzamide and *N,N*-diphenyl formamide do not form complexes, neither do they inhibit the reactions²⁸. In non-aqueous medium, water if added enhances the photoactivity of ZnO.

Yesodharan *et al*¹⁷ reported that ZnO prepared from carbonate and oxalate have a higher activity for the photocatalytic dehydrogenation of aliphatic alcohols. This is attributed to adsorbed CO₂, as ZnCO₃ itself was found to be an effective catalyst for such reactions. Adsorbed oxides of nitrogen, on the other hand, are found to decrease

the catalytic activity (ZnO prepared from nitrate salts). The authors suggest an initial polar intermediate in the reaction giving rise to a free radical in the solution as the reaction progresses.

In the case of the photoinduced catalytic reactions of aromatic primary amines, H-bonding plays a vital role^{10,20}. The reaction proceeds faster in aliphatic alcohols and acetone than in C₆H₅CH₂OH and hydrocarbon solvents. The azo compounds formed during the reaction inhibit the reaction because of their adsorption on ZnO.

Doping of ZnO with Al³⁺ is found to be beneficial while Li⁺ reduces the activity. This is for the formation of peroxide, whereas for the decomposition of peroxide the trend is reversed as it is a donor type reaction.

The following general mechanism is formulated.

Surface reaction for alcohols (RH) :

followed by homogeneous reaction in solution giving H₂O₂ and aldehyde or ketone via a free radical mechanism.

Surface reaction for the amine :

WO₃ :

The reactions of ethanol, methanol, isopropyl alcohol, aniline, formamide, dimethyl formamide, diethyl formamide, urea and benzamide have been investigated on WO₃. In the presence of formamide, the H₂O₂ concentration reached 10⁻⁴ g moles/lit within 1 hr. With other organic substrates like ethanol, methanol, 2-propanol and DMF, H₂O₂ could be detected only after 5 hr of irradiation. This shows that the reduction of oxygen is very slow in the presence of alcohols and other amides. This is in fact reflected in the low cathodic photocurrents and the sluggish response of WO₃ in a PEC cell in the presence of O₂ and organic substrates other

than formamide. A limiting concentration of H₂O₂ is reached with time of illumination. With increase in the concentration of HCONH₂ and decrease in the pH of the solution the yield of H₂O₂ increases. Experiments with free radical quenchers prove that part of the reaction is taking place through a free radical mechanism. In the absence of oxygen there is no production of H₂O₂. It is expected that excited electrons in the conduction band react with the adsorbed oxygen to form a superoxide ion which subsequently forms H₂O₂ through interaction with a proton.

Platinisation or copperisation of WO₃ particles decreases the yield of H₂O₂. It is because H₂O₂ decomposes at the metal site.

While ZnO is capable of producing H₂O₂ in the presence of a variety of organic substrates, WO₃ is active only in the presence of formamide. The mechanism of reactions on WO₃ is envisaged as follows²⁰.

Performance of the different electrode preparations:

The electrodes prepared by the methods described earlier give reproducible results. Even though all these electrodes are easy to prepare in the laboratory, some of them have certain disadvantages. The electrode prepared by painting a slurry on the metal foil and the electrode prepared from colloidal solution maintain only a loose contact between the oxide particle and the metal. Therefore some of the bare Pt surface will be in contact with the electrolyte. This prevents certain kind of studies like capacitance measurements being made, using these electrodes.

ZnO electrodes prepared with flux materials produced higher photocurrents suggesting a better contact between the particle and the metal.

However, the flux materials alter the catalytic properties of WO_3 and hence cannot be used for WO_3 . Several flux materials such as $ZnBr_2$, $ZnCl_2$, $CdCl_2$, $CdSO_4$, etc. have been tried. Among these only $CdCl_2$ is found useful as a flux for ZnO . WO_3 electrodes prepared by painting a paste and

heating at 400° also give good results. Short circuit photocurrent and open circuit photovoltage are found to depend on the temperature to which the WO_3 electrode is heated (Table 1).

The main disadvantage of the pellet electrodes as far as photoelectrocatalysis is concerned is that the sintering process always renders the ZnO less catalytically active. Heating WO_3 alters the stoichiometry of WO_3 and affects the catalytic activity.

The liquid crystals behaved as binders which are not photoelectrochemically active under the experimental conditions and it bound ZnO to give a better contact with both the metal and the solution. (Out of the two liquid crystals used cholesteryl oleate was found to be better). A comparison of different electrodes is given in Tables 2 and 3. WO_3 powder prepared by the decomposition of ammonium tungstate has the

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF HEAT TREATMENT OF WO_3 ELECTRODES ON SHORT CIRCUIT PHOTOCURRENT AND OPEN CIRCUIT PHOTOVOLTAGE

(Electrolyte : 0.1 M $HCONH_2$ in 0.1 M KCl)

Temp. °C	Colour of WO_3	Open circuit photovoltage (mV)		Photocurrent (μA)	
		O_2 atmosphere	N_2 atmosphere	O_2 atmosphere	N_2 atmosphere
200	Yellow	-385	+170	-21	2
400	Yellow	-460	+275	-25	2.5
600	Greenish yellow	-415	+200	-18	2.5
800	Green	+150	+170	+2.5	2.6

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF MODE OF PREPARATION OF ELECTRODES ON OPEN CIRCUIT PHOTOVOLTAGE AND SHORT CIRCUIT PHOTOCURRENT

(Electrolyte : 0.1 M $HCONH_2$ in 0.1 M KCl ; no external bias.
 V_{oc} - net open circuit photovoltage ; I_{sc} - Short circuit current)

No.	Type of the electrode	ZnO in N_2 atmosphere		WO_3			
		V_{oc}^f (mV)	I_{sc} (μA)	O_2 atmosphere		N_2 atmosphere	
				V_{oc} (mV)	I_{sc} (μA)	V_{oc} (mV)	I_{sc} (μA)
1.	Slurry or colloidal solution on Pt foil	590	80	-400	-20	150	2
2.	Painting and heating	-	-	(See Table 1)			
3.	Flux method	600	180	-325	-17	175	2.5
4.	Liquid crystal semiconductor	590	120	-	-	-	-
5.	Pellet	420	65	-5	-0.5	-	-
6.	WO_3 slurry on W foil	-	-	-	-0.5	-	-
7.	Oxide film on W foil	-	-	-5	-0.5	-	-

$f V_{oc}$ - Open circuit photovoltages quoted here are the net increase observed on illumination.

* For ZnO in O_2 atmosphere V_{oc} and I_{sc} show an initial cathodic value and later an anodic value. See Fig. 1.

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF NET OPEN CIRCUIT PHOTOVOLTAGE AND SHORT CIRCUIT PHOTOCURRENT OF THE CELL ON WO_3 OBTAINED FROM VARIOUS SOURCES

(Electrolyte : 0.1 M $HCONH_2$ in 0.1 M KCl)

No.	Source of WO_3	Net open circuit photovoltage (mV) ; O_2 atmosphere	Short circuit current
1.	Koch-Light	-420	-20
2.	BDH	-440	-21
3.	Prepared from sodium tungstate	-460	-22.5
4.	Prepared from W metal	-	-10

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE OF REDUCTION ON OPEN CIRCUIT PHOTOVOLTAGE (V_{oc}) AND SHORT CIRCUIT PHOTOCURRENT (I_{sc}) OF WO_3

(Electrolyte : 0.1 M $HCONH_2$ in 0.1 M KCl)

No.	Temp. of reduction with H_2 °C	Colour of the sample	V_{oc} (mV)		I_{sc} (μA)	
			O_2 atmosphere	N_2 atmosphere	O_2 atmosphere	N_2 atmosphere
1.	200	Green	-300	+30	-14	2.0
2.	400	Greenish blue	-10	+10	-1.0	1.5
3.	500	Blue	-5	+10	-0.5	0

maximum activity. As nonstoichiometry increased the activity decreased. The results are summarised in Table 4. WO_3 films formed by thermal or anodic oxidation of tungsten are found to be inactive. That it is the tungsten metal present as the conducting metal part in the electrode which makes the electrode inactive is inferred from the fact that unlike WO_3 paste painted on Pt foil, WO_3 paste painted on tungsten metal foil is not photo-catalytically active.

2. Photoelectrochemical studies on ZnO and WO_3 electrodes :

To make a comparison of the particulate and PEC systems, ZnO and WO_3 electrodes have been used in a PEC cell to carry out photoinduced catalytic reactions

The open circuit photovoltage and photocurrent are enhanced by the addition of organic substrates like alcohols, amines, amides, etc. to a ZnO photoelectrode compartment indicating a photo-catalytic reaction. However, WO_3 behaved in a different fashion as only a few substances reacted over WO_3 , notably $HCONH_2$ (cf. WO_3 particulate

system). The influence of the gaseous atmosphere in the electrode compartment has been reported earlier^{23,20}. It is very important to note that ZnO reacts with the organic substrate both in O₂ and N₂ atmosphere yielding the same products while WO₃ reacts with substances only in O₂ atmosphere.

The nature of photocurrent is also influenced by the gaseous atmosphere (Fig. 1) showing an electron

Fig. 1. Variation of photocurrent with time.

abstraction by O₂ in the anolyte, which is in good agreement with the suggested formation of super oxide anion. This is true for both WO₃ and ZnO, but it is the major electrode reaction with WO₃ as suggested by the observed net cathodic photocurrent. This may be because of the fact that the organic substance is neither getting oxidised by the holes in the valence band nor is the substance/intermediate radical formed supplying an electron to the conduction band of WO₃ to an extent to constitute a kinetically competitive anodic reaction.

Fig. 2. Photocurrent vs applied voltage for WO₃ electrode in N₂ and O₂ atmospheres.

The major reaction is the cathodic formation of a super oxide anion. In the case of ZnO, even though there is a cathodic reduction of O₂, the oxidation of the organic substance by the holes and the subsequent supply of an electron to the conduction band is kinetically more favourable. This is reflected in the production of a stable anodic current after the unstable initial cathodic current. The potentiostatic I-V curves in the case of ZnO also show cathodic photocurrents at lower potentials and thereafter well defined anodic currents at higher potentials unlike WO₃ (Figs. 2 and 3). It

Fig. 3. Photocurrent vs voltage curve for ZnO electrode in N₂ and O₂ atmospheres.

is clear that the cathodic reduction of O₂ is more favoured in WO₃. The reason why WO₃ is behaving like this is not clear from the energy level diagram (Fig. 4) since the levels pertaining to the

Fig. 4. Band edge positions of ZnO and WO₃ and solution redox levels relative to NHE at pH 2.

reactions of O₂ lie within the band gap of the oxide. There may be structural parameters of WO₃ and its surface which play an important role.

As the temperature of the PEC cell is increased the open circuit photovoltage and photocurrent

decreased. This may be because of the higher rate of desorption of adsorbed species at higher temperatures and the consequent substantial decrease of the catalytic activity. When the oxide is irradiated the excitation of electrons is dependent on the intensity of the light as well as the ability of the organic substrate to provide electrons to the holes. There is a linear relationship between the open circuit photovoltage and the logarithm of light intensity for both ZnO and WO₃ electrodes. A plot of open circuit photovoltage vs log light intensity is shown in Fig. 5 for ZnO.

Fig. 5. Effect of intensity of light on photovoltage.

Studies with doped ZnO :

When doping is done at 450° to avoid sintering, doping with Al³⁺ increased the photocurrent while Li⁺ decreased it. The catalytic activity of the doped samples was found to vary with the concentration of the dopant. The same behaviour is observed in particulate systems also. When the concentration of Al³⁺ was increased from 0.06 to 0.34 atom percentage there was an increase in the catalytic activity. But above that concentration the catalytic activity and the photocurrent decreased. It is understood that pure Al₂O₃ is a poor catalyst and not a semiconductor. Excess of Al₂O₃ present on the surface of ZnO will reduce the photocurrent and the catalytic activity. This is further supported by the observation in a separate experiment that Al₂O₃ added to ZnO brings down the rate of H₂O₂ formation. The presence of excess Al₂O₃ on the surface of ZnO arises due to the incomplete diffusion of Al³⁺ into the lattice under the conditions of doping. The sample is therefore heated again at 450° for 24 hr and an increase in the photocurrent is observed supporting this suggestion. The amount of H₂O₂ formed in a particulate system using the above sample also is found to increase by this heat treatment¹⁷. In the case of Li⁺ doped samples, the catalytic activity is found to decrease

with increase in the concentration of Li⁺ from 0.06 to 0.34 atom percentage. Further increase in the concentration of Li⁺ did not cause any further change in the catalytic activity.

The mechanism of these PEC reactions on ZnO and WO₃ electrodes have been described in detail in previous communications^{23,20}.

Conclusion :

The reactions taking place at the semiconductors, ZnO and WO₃, when they are used for photo-induced catalysis are identical with those taking place when these materials are used as photo-electrodes. The study of the electrical effects can therefore help in understanding and predicting the behaviour of these materials when used for carrying out photo-induced catalytic reactions.

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